

Morphological changes in host airway epithelium following SARS-CoV-2 infection: A pathophysiological perspective

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Abstract

COVID-19 continues to affect the world since its emergence, with new strains evolving during repeated summer and winter waves. The SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern (VOCs) show increased infective potential for the host due to mutations in their spike protein (S), which strengthens the binding between the target receptor of the spike protein, i.e., the angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE2), located on airway epithelial cells as well as other parts of the body like intestinal epithelial cells, thus allowing the virus to cause much more profound infection in the host cells. This review focuses on the progression of morphological changes in airway epithelial cells after exposure to SARS-CoV-2. The extent of damage or resilience in these cells is crucial in determining the degree of pathogenesis the virus can exert in the host body over time. We also examine recent cellular and animal models utilized to investigate the pathophysiology of SARS-CoV-2, which may provide new insights into its biology.

Key words: SARS-CoV-2, Epithelium, Lungs, Respiratory, COVID-19, Pathophysiology

Introduction

The common respiratory viruses target different airway epithelial cells, although airway epithelial cells serve as a barrier to defend against incoming viruses. The site of infection in lung airway epithelial cells by respiratory viruses is largely determined by the presence of a specific receptor being used by the virus for internalization. Viruses, such as influenza virus and coronaviruses, can also target alveolar cells. Epithelial cells recognize viral components and activate intrinsic cellular defences to restrict the infection.

General characteristics of the airway epithelia

The respiratory system begins with the nasal cavity and continues to the proximal section, which includes the trachea and the point where the trachea bifurcates into two bronchi at the fifth thoracic vertebra. Further, these bronchi give rise to many bronchioles, which are the conducting part (not involved in gaseous exchange). Finally, the transitional bronchioles give rise to alveoli, forming the exchange part where CO₂ is exchanged for O₂. The lining of the human respiratory system houses a myriad of cell types, with diverse structures and functions. While the majority of airway epithelial cells function as a barrier to external agents like chemicals, aerosols, and pathogens, some specialized cells perform more intricate functions like mucus secretion, gaseous exchange, neuroendocrine signalling, etc. Figure 1 summarizes the various types of airway epithelial cells and their location.

CELL TYPE	LOCATION
Ciliated columnar epithelial cell	Throughout the conducting airway from trachea to bronchioles
Goblet cell	Mostly in proximal airway, decrease progressively towards smaller bronchioles
Serous cells	Distal to mucous cells in submucosal glands of proximal airway or as surface serous cells
Basal epithelial cell	Only in the conducting airway epithelium, till large bronchioles
Clara cells	Concentrated in the distal conducting airway and bronchioles
Immune cells	Throughout the airway epithelium, within the epithelial layer and underlying mucosa
Alveolar type I cells	In the alveolar ducts and alveolar sacs
Alveolar type II cells	Scattered among type I cells, in the corners of alveolar septa
Pulmonary neuroendocrine cells (PNECs)	Throughout the conducting airway, from trachea to terminal bronchioles

Figure 1: The types of airway epithelial cells and their locations in the human respiratory system (Created in: www.biorender.com)

The function of these cells mainly depends on their architecture and location. Detailed accounts on the function of these cells have already been reviewed. (Crystal et al., 2008; Knight & Holgate, 2003; Proud, 2008). Discussing about the morphology of these cells one by one, the ciliated cells are relatively translucent due to their lack of secretory products or mucus granules and have multiple mitochondria at the apical portion while cilia are found on the luminal side of these cells (Watson & Brinkman, n.d.). Goblet cells on the other hand, have an opaque cytoplasm due to mucus granules (Mariassy et al., 1988).

The serous cells are categorized into two types: surface serous cells and serous gland cells. Both types feature a pyramidal shape, with dense secretory granules located in the apical region and a nucleus positioned in the basal region. Additionally, multivesicular bodies are also observed. (Meyrick & Reid, 1970). As the name suggests, basal cells form a monolayer along the basement membrane and giving a pseudostratified appearance to the epithelium. They have a large indented nuclei filling most of the cell volume and their cytoplasm contains multiple ribosomes and mitochondria glycogen granules(Proud, 2008). Clara cells are columnar in shape

having a central nucleus, prominent Golgi and granular ER. They are easily identifiable by the membrane bound dense secretory granules (Plopper & Hyde, 2015). Alveolar type I cells are flattened cells, with each cell having a small nucleus surrounded by a few small mitochondria, an inconspicuous Golgi apparatus, and some cisternae of endoplasmic reticulum with ribosomes. Pinocytotic vesicles are also easily observed in the peripheral cytoplasm. Alveolar type II cells are more cuboidal in shape, having a polarized structure due to existence of tight junctions at the lateral cell surface. The apical surface also has microvilli as a striking feature. Pulmonary neuroendocrine cells (PNEC) are spindle shaped, with their basal part facing the basement membrane and a thin apical process towards the epithelium. Large number of dense vesicles strongly stained in electron microscopy by silver atoms, are concentrated at the base of PNECs (Proud, 2008).

Making contact: Initial interaction of the virus with the epithelial cells

It is known how SARS-CoV-2 exploits human airway epithelium by infecting ciliated cells; recent studies are suggesting its dynamic nature and use of ciliated cell differentiation intermediates. High-resolution images suggest that the virus establishes and sustains infection via two key cell types from the same cell lineage: newly formed ciliated cells (NIC) and virus-rich intermediate cells (VIC). Early during infection, SARS-CoV-2 targets progenitor-derived ciliated lineage intermediate cells expressing both ACE-2 receptor and TMPRSS2, which are also present on microvilli. NICs are transcriptionally distant transient population of infected ciliated cells that emerge after virus exposure and are characterized by a nearly 100% virus infection rate and potentially the secretion of pro-differentiation paracrine cues such as the expression of TGF- β 2, BMP4, and WNT5A. These signals act on proximal basal cells to upregulate the differentiation of basal stem cells towards ciliated lineage, thereby increasing the virus infection targeting and reducing the number of long-term basal progenitor cells, making the tissue more susceptible to virus infection (Greaney et al., 2023).

As the infection progresses, airway epithelial cells are dominated by virus-rich intermediates (VRI); this continuous differentiation state between basal and ciliated cells is maintained from 2-28 days post infection. VRI cells exhibit unique features that makes the environment more favourable towards sustenance of virus infection; high adsorption of virus during early stages, upregulation of interferon stimulated genes without virus clearance and suppression of apoptosis via upregulation of BCL2. A subset of VRIs also arise during this stage with nearly 100% infection rate with low expression of ACE-2 suggesting involvement in sustenance of

virus infection rather than newer infections. VRIs are also involved in structural remodelling of cells such as upregulation of microvilli regulatory proteins EZR and VIL1 and ciliated associated motor proteins increasing the lateral virus infection in epithelia. Thus, these changes increase the membrane area for virion budding amplifying the virus output and spread to adjacent susceptible cells(Kim & Lee, 2024).

VRIs also influence their microenvironment. They secrete extracellular nicotinamide phosphoribosyl transferase (NAMPT) which exhibits cytokine like immune activation, they induce extracellular matrix components such as collagen type I alpha 1, encoded by the COL1A1 gene that activate integrin-mediated Akt/PI3K survival pathways; and they express Ephrin ligands that modulate cell–cell communication in differentiation cells. Along with vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGFA) signalling which increases basal cell proliferation by VEGF receptor 2 signalling. These factors remodel the epithelial landscape, supporting the continuous production of VRIs sustaining infection. Consistently pathway analysis shows high expression of MAPK signalling which is known to upregulate the epithelial regeneration, cytoskeletal organisation and virus replication cumulatively suggesting the remodelling of airway epithelium in which basal-intermediate-ciliated lineage transitions are upregulated while staying highly resistant towards apoptosis(Kim & Lee, 2024).

SARS CoV-2's tendency to infect differentiating basal cells has major effect on how airway epithelia respond to SARS CoV-2. At initial stages, virus enhances the mucociliary functions increasing the lateral flow of virus in epithelia. By 3-4 days post infection loss of mature ciliated and basal progenitor cells lead to disruption of epithelial barrier leading to deeper penetration of virus in lower airways contributing to disease severity. These findings explain why children tend to do better than adults. Kids have more active airway stem cells and faster epithelial turnover, so they can quickly replace infected intermediate cells and prevent long-lasting viral niches. Adults, especially older adults have slower repair systems, making it easier for infected progenitor-like cells to persist (Pinto et al., 2022)

Correlation of morphological observations with SARS-CoV-2 pathophysiology

Nose is the primary entry site of corona virus. The surface of nose is lined by pseudostratified columnar epithelium which include ciliated cells, non-ciliated (secretory cells), mucus secreting goblet cells, basal cells which are a type of stem cells, and some rare neuroepithelial

cells (Whitsett & Alenghat, 2015). Nasal epithelium remains intact and continues to retain the virus maintaining productive infection for several days exacerbating epithelial stress, inflammation and chronic tissue alterations. Following SARS CoV-2 infection, the cellular landscape is changed inducing heterogeneity in nasal epithelial cells leading to the emergence of a distinct stress induced subset of cells DDIT3^{high} cluster expressing high level of stress or ER stress-related genes, DDIT3, ATF3. Despite the extreme load of virus, these cells will have a dampened anti-viral IFN response but shows increased cell death driven by ER stress pathways, TNF alpha and NFκB signaling. Dynamic sampling experiments have also confirmed that virus has a longer half-life in human mucus, remains stable and survives for extended period outside the cells (Gamage et al., 2022).

scRNA sequence analysis tools report that the cellular composition of nasal epithelium remains perturbed even after the clearance of viral infection in patients with severe post-COVID syndrome. The epithelial cells were reported to be depleted in these cases, with deregulation of several inflammatory pathways such as TNFα, TGFβ, and NF-κB via the MIF (macrophage migration inhibitory factor) signalling axis. Deregulated TNFα suggests chronic immune activation inducing cell death/stress in epithelial cells, which appears to be irreversible, as the altered cellular composition does not return to normal state due to increased TNFα levels preventing the repair of the mucosal barrier. This impaired regeneration of ciliated and goblet cells from basal cells results in reduced mucosal ciliary clearance. Additionally, insulin growth factor (IGF), which is known to promote differentiation and tissue repair, was found to be absent in severe post-COVID patients. These events prevent restoration of nasal epithelium even long after viral clearance, posing greater risk for future respiratory infections. (Reddy et al., 2025)

Conducting airways

From the nasal passage the virus enters the conducting airways by micro aspiration of virus containing pharyngeal secretions and infect the ACE 2 and TMPRSS2 expressing epithelial cells which include ciliated, mucus secreting, and club cells. Primary infection in the bronchial epithelia cells was reported to occur in ciliated cells followed by secretory cells. Ciliated cells were infected more as compared to goblet cells. Following infection, immediate damage of ciliated cells was not seen, but mucus producing goblet cell population was increased (Mulay et al., 2021). On the other hand, type I and II stimulatory cells were reported to be increased in infected ciliated cells (Ravindra et al., 2021) by scRNA sequence analysis. Several other

studies have reported the absence of anti-viral response in airway tissues post infection with almost undetectable level of interferons in bronchial epithelial cells with CXCL 10 expression at moderate level (Blanco-Melo et al., 2020).

Live cells imaging of ALI (air liquid interface) cultures infected with SARS-CoV-2 had demonstrated the presence of the virus in the ciliated and mucus cells, and as long as the cilia are active and intact, the virus spread was not random but rather formed a comet-like streak along the epithelial surface and moved slowly in the direction of mucus flow. Whereas, it was restricted with an application of agarose on the epithelial layer. This was further confirmed by knocking out two genes, DNAH5 and DNAI1, which are known to play a role in the beating of cilia. Silencing of these two genes had shown extremely slow and steady spread compared to the control groups, however, it did not impact the cilia formation. These reports collectively suggest that the cilia, which normally help to clear the infection, are exploited by the virus to facilitate its spread further. In the later phase of infection, the shedding of cilia potentially inhibits the virus spread as the mucus gets thicker, inhibiting its flow. With the loss of ciliated cells, the mucus starts accumulating, clogging the airway, thus increasing the inflammation. Mucus flow initially transmits the virus, but as mucociliary clearance deteriorates and cells begin to die, mucus also serves as a barrier, preventing the virus from entering new target cells. (Becker et al., 2024).

Gas exchange units

Type II alveolar cells (AT2) are more SUSCEPTIBLE to SARS CoV-2 infection due to their increased expression of ACE 2 receptors and TMPRSS2 compared to type I cells (AT1) (Mulay et al., 2021) causing more damage to AT2 cells. During the process, type I cells also get damaged intensely. However, much of the damage of type I alveolar cells and the endothelial cell lining, the alveolar capillaries are not due to direct viral cytopathic effect, rather due to the exaggerated inflammatory response generated following infection of type II alveolar cells (Hou et al., 2020). As AT2 cells acts as stemlike cells for AT1 cells and surfactant production, the excessive damage caused following SARS CoV-2 infection disrupts the regeneration of lung alveolar cells leading to reduced surfactant production, progressive alveolar collapse, hypoxia and increased rate of morbidity and mortality in COVID19 patients (Juil et al., 2020).

Studies carried out in mouse models using scRNA sequencing tools had demonstrated that during recovery, the AT2 cells had shown temporary transition to intermediate states during transition to AT1 state, such as alveolar differentiation intermediates (ADI), damage-associated transient progenitors (DATP) and Pre-AT1 transitional state (PATS) which may facilitate repair. But if transition fails from AT2 to AT1, these intermediate cells accumulate and lead to fibrosis and tissue remodeling.

In the mouse infected with a mouse adapted SARS-CoV-2 strain, special type of macrophages, pro-fibrotic monocyte-derived macrophages and persistently activated B- cells were observed long after infection. DSP (Digital Spatial Profiling) analysis of macrophages showed increased expression of genes associated with fibrotic signaling, tissue remodeling and macrophage survival. The persistently activated adaptive immune signaling and fibrotic macrophages keep releasing signals that promote remodeling and scarring of human lungs.

At early stages of infection in mice, both AT2 cells and bronchial epithelial cell regions showed up regulated IFN stimulatory genes, indicating elevated inflammatory and anti-viral response. Thus, the up regulated inflammatory response resulted in loss of certain marker genes involved in biological oxidation pathways and surfactant synthesis by AT2 cells critical for maintaining airway function and preventing alveolar collapse and proper gas exchange respectively.

At later stages, hallmarks of chronic lung injury such as fibrotic remodeling and damaged repair were observed. Transcriptomics analysis revealed cellular senescence, hypoxia signaling, complement activation, TGF-beta signaling and p53 damage response. Besides above findings, difference in terms of the level of apoptosis between bronchial epithelial cells and alveolar cells was noted. The bronchial cells showed cleaved caspase-3, indicating that these cells undergo programmed and controlled cell death to restrict the viral spread. On the contrary, alveolar cells that showed little or no caspase 3 activation suggesting limited apoptosis promoting inflammation and increased tissue damage (Dinnon et al., 2022).

Models used to depict changes in morphology and physiology of infected cells

The use of models in SARS-CoV-2 infection allows the study of phenomena such as viral entry, replication, and as is relevant to this review, morphological changes associated with viral infection in the airway epithelial cells. The different model systems are shown comprehensively in Figure-2.

Figure 2. *In vitro* [Pires, 2022 (1); P Wang, 2020 (4); JW Yang, 2022 (5); Cortese, 2022 (6), Pinto, 2022 (7), Zhu, 2020 (8), Mergio, 2022 (9), Han, 2022 (10), R Wang, 2022 (11)]; *In vivo* [Lee, 2021 (2), MS Yang, 2021 (12)], and primate models [Kwon, 2024 (3), Santana, 2021 (13)] being used currently to study SARS-CoV-2 pathophysiology

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In-vitro cellular systems complemented with imaging and proteomics techniques like confocal microscopy, TEM, western blotting and mass spectrometry and advanced assays like cilia beat analysis, TEER assay (Robinot et al., 2021) provide a detailed view of how the SARS-CoV-2 exerts its effects on the cells of upper as well as the lower respiratory tract. Organoid studies mimic the airway morphology in a much-sophisticated way than the 2D cultured cells, as they involve multicellular systems, like the Alveolar lung organoids (Han et al., 2022), and have since helped to lay the foundation for discovery of multiple therapeutics. Drug efficacy testing (Wang et al., 2022) using iPSC derived human airway lineages has been a recent approach to solving the SARS-CoV-2 crisis. Small animal models enable whole organ resolution for preliminary testing of drugs and establishment of proposed signalling cascades using flow cytometry, and require more than one model to ascertain the validity of data obtained from *in-vitro* studies (da Costa et al., 2022). Non-human primates replicate the branching of proximal and distal airway and hence are considered most relevant in terms of translational efficiency of results, which are finally grounded by the autopsy analysis of human samples using TEM (Santana et al., 2021) or immunohistochemical staining.

Conclusion

The profound modulation of host airway epithelium by SARS-CoV-2 influences key characteristics of the cells, including membrane and cytoskeleton remodelling, impaired immune signalling, and generation of multiple intermediate cellular and organellar components. This directly relates to viral entry as well as pathogenesis by influencing its replication and persistence in the host. Eventually, the environment created by the virus inside the airway leads to long-term injury and fibrosis inside the alveoli, which further exposes individuals to what is being termed now as long COVID. Continued research on the viral pathology using *in vitro* as well as *in vivo* models will be required to decipher the dynamics of viral infection and to develop targeted therapeutics that could restore the epithelial homeostasis.

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